

Supplemental A

1.1. Complete Mathematical Formulation of the Proposed Framework

• Feature Matrix and Composite Scores

The full encoded feature matrix concatenates all survey blocks as follows:

$$X = [L \mid O \mid C \mid N \mid E \mid \gamma] \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times p} \quad (1)$$

Where L = Likert items (10-dimensional), O = tailored organizational items (4-dimensional), C = compliance items (5-dimensional), N = numerical items, E = one-hot encoded items, and γ = country indicator.

Three composite safety scores are appended to X as supplementary features:

$$SS_i = \frac{1}{10} \sum_j L_{ij} \in [1,5] \quad (2)$$

$$CS_i = \sum_m C_{im} \in \{0,1,2,3,4,5\} \quad (3)$$

• Target Variable Construction

The three-class risk label is derived from the parsed accident count a_i :

$$y_i = \begin{cases} 0 \text{ (Low)} & \text{if } a_i = 0 \\ 1 \text{ (Med)} & \text{if } 1 \leq a_i \leq 5 \\ 2 \text{ (High)} & \text{if } a_i \geq 6 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The binary label applied to the Pakistan dataset to address class imbalance is defined as:

$$y_i^b = \begin{cases} 0 \text{ (Low Risk)} & \text{if } a_i = 0 \\ 1 \text{ (At-Risk)} & \text{if } a_i \geq 1 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

• Random Forest and Class-Weight Balancing

The majority-vote prediction over $T = 200$ trees is:

$$\hat{y}_i = \operatorname{argmax}_c \sum_t \mathbf{1}\{h_t(x_i) = c\}, c \in \{0,1,2\} \quad (6)$$

Class weights are inversely proportional to class frequency to address imbalance:

$$w_c = \frac{n_{train}}{C \times n_c}, \sum_c w_c \cdot n_c = n_{train} \quad (7)$$

22 The weighted Gini impurity used at each tree split node M is:

$$23 \quad G_w(\mathcal{M}) = \sum_c w_c \times p_{\mathcal{M}c}(1 - p_{\mathcal{M}c}) \quad (8)$$

24 • **Evaluation Metrics**

25 The macro F1-score used for cross-country transfer experiments assigns equal weight to all classes:

$$26 \quad F1_{macro} = \frac{1}{C} \sum_c F1_c \quad (9)$$

27 • **NLP Feature Formulations**

28 The TF-IDF weight for term j in document i (log-normalized with smoothed IDF) is:

$$29 \quad \lambda_{ij} = \frac{\left[1 + \log(f_{ij})\right] \times \left[\log\left(\frac{n+1}{df_j+1}\right) + 1\right]}{\|\Lambda_i\|_2} \quad (10)$$

30 The LDA generative model with $K = 3$ topics is specified as:

$$31 \quad \theta_i \sim Dir(\alpha); z_{il} \sim Cat(\theta_i); w_{il} \sim Cat(\beta_{z_{il}}) \quad (11)$$

32 Text Blob sentiment polarity is computed as a lexicon-based, context-modified score:

$$33 \quad s_i = \frac{1}{m} \sum_w \mu(w) \cdot \gamma(context(w)) \in [-1, +1] \quad (12)$$

34 • **Hybrid Model and Cross-Country Transfer**

35 The augmented feature matrix combining structured survey features and NLP blocks is:

$$36 \quad X' = [X \mid \Lambda \mid \Theta \mid s] \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times (p+104)} \quad (13)$$

37 The cross-country transfer protocol applies the source country scaler to the target country data under a
38 zero-shot scenario:

$$39 \quad \tilde{X}_C = \frac{X_C - \mu_P}{\sigma_P}; \Delta F1^{P \rightarrow C} = 0.11 - 0.85 = -0.74 \quad (14)$$

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Supplemental B

41 **2.1. Survey Instrument Design and Data Collection**

42 The survey questionnaire addressed key safety factors identified in the construction literature as predictors
 43 of accidents. This questionnaire had 48 items across seven blocks of themes, as shown in **Error! Not a**
 44 **valid bookmark self-reference..**

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Table 1: Survey Instrument Structure and Item Categories

Block	Content Domain	Item Type / Scale
Block 1 (Q1–10)	Respondent profile: country, age, education, experience, role, organization, project type	Categorical / Nominal
Block 2 (Q11–20)	Safety climate perception: training adequacy, PPE availability, worker fatigue, site audits, lighting/ventilation, budget limits	5-point Likert (1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree)
Block 3 (Q21–24)	Organizational safety factors: capital investment, management capability, financial constraints, technology adoption	5-point Likert-type rating scale
Block 4 (Q25–39)	Accident causes, PPE gaps, training methods, technologies used, and project characteristics.	Multiple-Choice (Single / Multi-Select)
Block 5 (Q40–44)	Compliance indicators: hazardous zone marking, free PPE provision, violation penalties	Binary (Yes / No)
Block 6 (Q45–47)	Quantitative site metrics: accident count, safety meetings per month, PPE importance rating	Numerical / Count
Block 7 (Q48)	Open-ended safety suggestions and qualitative remarks	Free-text (NLP input)

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47 **2.2. Evaluation Metrics and Validation Strategy**

48 The framework consisted of three steps: (1) 5-fold stratified cross-validation (CV) on the training set to
 49 estimate the model's generalization and to adjust class-weights; (2) final test on the stratified 20% hold-
 50 out test set; and (3) cross-country transfer to the complete counterpart dataset to estimate out-of-
 51 distribution performance. Table 2 provides an overview.

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Table 2: Summary of Evaluation Protocol

Evaluation Level	Data Used	Purpose
Level 1: Cross-Validation	80% training set, 5-fold stratified	Hyperparameter tuning, generalization estimation
Level 2: Test Set Evaluation	20% held-out test set (stratified split)	Final model performance reporting
Level 3: Cross-Country Transfer	Full complementary national dataset	Out-of-distribution generalization assessment

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Supplemental C

55 **3.1. Research Design and Overall Framework**

56 In this research study, we employ a quantitative, cross-sectional research framework grounded in
57 the positivist paradigm. The study employed a structured questionnaire as a key data-collection tool
58 to measure various safety-related constructs among a large, geographically dispersed group of
59 construction professionals. A cross-sectional design was chosen because it allows efficient data
60 collection at a given point in time and facilitates comparative analysis across two national contexts,
61 Pakistan and China, using a unified modeling approach.

62 The methodological approach comprises three phases, as shown in Figure 1. Phase 1 involved
63 designing the survey questionnaire based on a review of existing scales measuring safety climate
64 and construction-specific hazards, collecting data from 300 people (150 in each country), and
65 encoding it into a structured feature matrix. In phase two, separate machine learning models were
66 developed for each country using encoded data, evaluated using cross-validation and test sets, and
67 interpreted using SHAP analysis. In the third phase, NLP methods were used to analyze survey
68 responses, extracting sentiment and topic features, which were then combined with the structured
69 features to create a hybrid model.

70 **3.2. Survey Instrument Design and Data Collection**

71 The survey questionnaire addressed key safety factors identified in the construction literature as
72 predictors of accidents. This questionnaire had 48 items across seven blocks of themes. It was
73 developed using well-established scales, such as the Nordic Occupational Safety Climate
74 Questionnaire (NOSACQ-50) and the Construction Safety Climate Survey (CSCS). It was
75 subsequently modified to include items specific to Pakistan and China's regulatory and operational
76 frameworks.

79 Figure 1: Proposed framework system architecture, describing four functional modules: (1) input
80 data layer, (2) feature integration module, (3) ML core model module, and (4) output module.

81 To assess the clarity of the questionnaire, the interpretability of the responses, and the time required
82 to complete it, a pilot study was conducted with 20 construction professionals (10 from each
83 country) to evaluate both questionnaires. The pilot evaluation was based on feature completeness,

84 response consistency, missing-data behaviour, class distribution stability, and compatibility with
85 downstream preprocessing flows, rather than the more traditional psychometric internal-
86 consistency measures. Ambiguous wording, an unbalanced distribution of responses across
87 categories, and the general quality of predictive input features for subsequent machine learning
88 analysis were improved based on feedback received during the pilot phase. The final questionnaire
89 was disseminated through professional Associations, Construction companies, Engineering
90 societies, Project offices and academic institutions in Pakistan (Peshawar, Lahore, Islamabad,
91 Karachi) and China (Dalian, Shanghai, Chongqing, Shenzhen, Beijing). 300 valid responses were
92 received, yielding a 86.7% response rate (150 responses per country). The demographics are shown
93 in Figure 2.

94 **3.3. *Pakistan Model Improvement Journey***

95 The contribution of each step is explicitly captured. The five steps of optimization led to
96 improvements in the Pakistan F1-score from 0.38 to 0.65 (a gain of 0.27) and in accuracy from 0.46
97 to 0.73 (a gain of 0.27). Binary classification (+0.05) provided the biggest single-step F1-score jump,
98 followed by class-weight sample re-weighting (+0.09) and incorporating composite aggregate
99 features (+0.06). These results validate the need for dataset-level and algorithm-level adjustments
100 to learn and predict from imbalanced, low-data survey data, typical of construction safety studies in
101 the developing world. The underlying reasons for this performance gap, rooted in regulatory and
102 operational differences between the two countries, are discussed in Section 5.1. The contribution of
103 each step is explicitly captured. The gradual improvement in F1-score and accuracy is shown in Figure 3
104 for five rounds of model improvement.

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(n = 300 Construction Professionals – Pakistan & China)

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Figure 2: A demographic overview of the survey: (a) country distribution; (b) Project Type Involvement; (c) education level by country; (d) years of experience by country.

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Figure 3: Line chart tracing the enhancement in F1-score (solid blue) and accuracy (dashed red) for the Pakistan model